

Identifying the Risks Associated with Public Wi-Fi Networks and How Users Can Protect Themselves Against Them

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11/04/2025

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Abstract

Public Wi-Fi networks are present in countless urban environments and are utilised by many. However, there are significant security risks associated with them, with most users unaware of the full extent. This project examines how the Wi-Fi protocol has changed over time and what vulnerabilities remain prevalent. An investigation is performed into user behaviour and what compels individuals to connect to public Wi-Fi networks, and proposes practical threat mitigation techniques users can take. This study comprises a thematic literature review of existing scientific papers and industry journals covering both technical and behavioural elements of this topic. The resulting recommendations span changing user habits, enforcing safety standards and strengthening underlying technologies. Despite all efforts by the industry so far, this topic still presents significant concerns that need to be continually addressed.

1 Introduction

This paper will identify the ongoing and emerging security risks associated with public Wi-Fi networks, relating to both technical vulnerabilities and user behaviour. It will then outline how users can protect themselves against potential threats. Today, public Wi-Fi networks are commonplace, yet the average user remains unaware of vulnerabilities that can be exploited, including both targeted and opportunistic attacks by cybercriminals. The impact on individuals can be severe, ranging from privacy breaches to financial loss. This paper will investigate user behaviour and motivations, analyse the security features within the 802.11 Wi-Fi protocol, and examine various attack methods. Additionally, corresponding mitigation techniques will be identified. A review of available academic research surrounding this topic will be conducted, and the findings synthesised to support deeper analysis. This paper aims to contribute to public awareness of the risks associated with insecure Wi-Fi networks and provide practical steps that users can take to protect themselves.

2 Project Summary

In the modern world, public Wi-Fi networks are widely used in environments such as shops, cafes, airports and train stations. They are appealing to individuals for several reasons, but are not always inherently safe. In fact, they commonly lack adequate security, which puts users at risk. This project aims to identify the risks associated with insecure public Wi-Fi networks and how these risks can be mitigated. This report will investigate public Wi-Fi networks and the user behaviour that surrounds them. It looks to explore and break down the protocols that make up Wi-Fi, examining how the technology has evolved over time against an ever-changing landscape. It will identify some of the attacks possible on public Wi-Fi networks, and explain what this means for the end user. This will allow the impact that successful attacks have on individuals to be explored. As a final objective, the project outlines practical steps users can take to protect themselves against these threats.

3 Business Need/Case

3.1 Problem Background

In virtually any public space there will be numerous Wi-Fi networks operating at any one time. Many of these are offered by businesses to provide convenience and encourage customers to visit. As more of our daily lives take place online, this makes it a target for cyber criminals. The average non-technical user does not understand the extent of the risk and will unknowingly expose their sensitive data. This can have both emotional and financial impact on individuals and businesses. With a reduction in cyber-crime on public Wi-Fi networks, fewer financial reimbursements will have to be made by banks in the aftermath of an attack.

3.2 Market Needs

There is an urgent requirement for secure networking in the current market. Individuals use the internet, regardless of the medium (e.g. home/public Wi-Fi, cellular connection etc.), for a variety of activities. These include financial account management, accessing sensitive files stored in the cloud, sending and receiving confidential messaging via emails and instant messaging services, and purchasing physical or virtual goods. Despite improvements in Wi-Fi security, many enhancements are not always realised in practice, as a significant number of networks still use outdated technology. More recently, regulation has been applied to organisations to enforce cybersecurity standards to protect users. Improving public awareness on this topic will enable individuals to make more informed decisions and operate safely online.

3.3 Benefits

With many attacks targeting financial services, such as online banking, reducing risks on public Wi-Fi networks will result in reduced monetary loss for businesses and individuals. There is also a less quantifiable, but still significant, impact of personal data or files being exposed in data breaches. Businesses are incentivised to offer secure public Wi-Fi networks to protect their reputation. If customers experience an attack whilst using their services, they may be blamed if perceived to have neglected adequate network security measures. Overall, this project aims to contribute to the general Wi-Fi security ecosystem by making improved security policies more commonplace in society.

3.4 Dis-Benefits

There are potential drawbacks associated with this project. The mitigation techniques established could be impractical for users or businesses to implement for several reasons. This could include significant costs associated with implementing more secure infrastructure, either having to be absorbed by the business or passed on to customers (i.e. removal of free Wi-Fi). Methods for users to protect themselves could be technologically challenging and create a barrier for less tech-savvy users. Additionally, the measures a user must take could detract from the convenience of using Wi-Fi networks in public. There is also a risk that, after the project's objectives are achieved and users adopt some basic protection methods, they continue to engage in risky behaviour due to a false sense of security.

3.5 Approximate Budget / Time

This project is estimated to take 8-10 weeks to complete all aspects of the research and analysis process. This is divided into the following deliverables:

- Planning and preliminary research: 2-3 weeks
- Literature collection and review: 3-4 weeks
- Research methodology: 1 week
- Presentation of findings: 1 week
- Write up and conclusion: 1 week

The project is not expected to incur any costs due to sufficient literature being available free of charge for the student due to academic licenses already being provided by the university.

4 Work Breakdown Structure (WBS)

Figure 1: Work Breakdown Structure Chart

5 Gantt Chart

Month	Feb					Mar					
Week Commencing	27	3	10	17	24	3	10	17	24	31	7
1. Project Planning											
1.1 Conduct preliminary research											
1.2 Define aims and objectives											
1.3 Generate research questions											
2. Introduction											
2.1 Describe background											
2.2 Explore market needs											
2.3 Determine benefits and risks											
3. Literature Review											
3.1 Collect related papers											
3.2 Perform initial readings											
3.3 Establish key points											
3.4 Critically analyse findings											
4. Research Methodology											
4.1 Define research framework											
4.2 Describe selection criteria											
4.3 Explain data organisation and analysis											
5. Findings and Discussion											
5.1 Summarise key themes											
5.2 Identify research gaps											
5.3 Propose recommendations											
6. Presentation											
6.1 Create slides											
6.2 Prepare speaking points and re-hearse											
6.3 Present											
7. Closeout and Final Submission											
7.1 Write conclusion											
7.2 Self-reflection											
7.3 Final edits and proofreading											
7.4 Submit report											

6 Literature Review

6.1 Introduction

The 802.11 Wi-Fi standard was first introduced in 1997 (Schoendorff, 2022), which has led to extensive literature covering the subject in detail. These works cover a variety of topics, with this project specifically focussing on the technical features of the Wi-Fi protocols and how they have developed over time. The number of public Wi-Fi hotspots exceeded 47 million in 2014 (R. Sharma, 2014) and has since increased to over 539 million in 2023 (Redway Networks, n.d.). Therefore, there has been ample opportunity for public Wi-Fi security to be studied in more depth and a large amount of high-quality literature has been produced. Literature relevant to this project will be reviewed below.

6.2 Review of 10 Related Literature

Project Keywords Used:

Public Wi-Fi security, WEP WPA WPA2 WPA3 vulnerabilities, Public Wi-Fi user behaviour, Public Wi-Fi security best practices, Global Wi-Fi security trends

The Evolution of 802.11 Wireless Security (Benton, 2010)

Thanks to widespread adoption of Wi-Fi, the 802.11 protocol has been studied in depth. 802.11 has evolved over time, beginning with WEP. This had several encryption flaws and was highly vulnerable to being cracked. WPA introduced the TKIP protocol, but at the time it was still vulnerable to brute force dictionary attacks on passphrases. This brought on the development of its successor, WPA2, which incorporated AES encryption and the stronger CCMP protocol (Benton, 2010). This work provides a concise overview of the first iterations of the 802.11 protocol but focuses on flaws with the protocol itself, rather than exploring user risks, which is the focus of this project.

A Survey on Wireless Security Protocols (Lashkari, Danesh, and Samadi, 2009)

Lashkari, Danesh, and Samadi (2009) expands on this by examining the security issues prevalent in older protocols, such as WEP's poor encryption and WPA's vulnerability stemming from reusing keys. WPA2 introduced improvements, however the PSK (pre-shared key) mechanism means it's still susceptible to dictionary attacks (Lashkari, Danesh, and Samadi, 2009). This report provides a thorough overview of known vulnerabilities across the generations of the 802.11 protocol but again lacks relation to risks for users.

Wireless Security Protocols WPA3: A Systematic Literature Review (Halbouni, Ong, and Leow, 2023)

Today, the latest iteration is WPA3, the most secure Wi-Fi protocol to date. As a result, more recent examinations of the Wi-Fi landscape focus on the state of WPA3. It is engineered to resist dictionary attacks possible in WPA2, due to SAE (Simultaneous Authentication of Equals) for key exchange. However, WPA3 is not faultless and still has many vulnerabilities explored by researchers. These include evil twin access points, downgrade attacks and side channel exploits. With that said, WPA3 represents several notable improvements over WPA2, but it is not perfect. It is currently suffering from slow adoption rates due to limitations on legacy hardware and widespread compatibility issues, so its benefits are not yet widely recognised in practice. The authors recommend improving backwards compatibility to encourage wider adoption of more secure protocols (Halbouni, Ong, and Leow, 2023). This paper highlights

WPA3 from a technical standpoint, but does not directly look at implications on user security.

A Comprehensive Attack Flow Model and Security Analysis for Wi-Fi and WPA3 (Kohlilos and Hayajneh, 2018)

From the early stages of Wi-Fi to today, there have always been attack methods combatted in newer protocols. This begins the next iteration of vulnerability discovery and countermeasure development. One such attack vector is MiTM (man-in-the-middle) attacks, allowing communication to be intercepted between source and destination. WEP and WPA/WPA2 were found to be susceptible to MiTM due to poor encryption. Likewise, even WPA3's transition mode is vulnerable to attacks, like when the compatibility feature forces a downgrade to WPA2 instead of WPA3, leaving users exposed to the associated vulnerabilities (Kohlilos and Hayajneh, 2018). The authors offer a strong overview of how attacks have persisted through the various iterations of the protocol, but only give limited attention to the role of user awareness in enabling or preventing such attacks, a key focus of this project.

The Rise of Public Wi-Fi and Threats (Dabhade, Patil, and K. Sharma, 2023)

Aside from vulnerabilities in the protocols themselves, there are numerous prevalent threats against users within real world scenarios. The authors identify motivating factors for users to connect to a public Wi-Fi network include the lack of cost, and to perform certain heavy-bandwidth tasks like downloading large files (Dabhade, Patil, and K. Sharma, 2023). The report makes valid points and theorises some likely motives for users connecting to public Wi-Fi networks, but its recommended safety measures are only targeted at the user, rather than those providing the network.

Why do people use public Wi-Fi? An investigation of risk-taking behavior and factors leading to decisions (Abdulkader, 2023)

This psychological element is further explored by other researchers and observations on behaviour are reported. One significant factor identified is 'optimism bias', meaning a user would connect to a network, despite any possible risks, because they believe they are less likely to be targeted by a hacker compared to another user. It's also stated that users knowingly connect to risky Wi-Fi networks due to convenience and cost saving factors. Surveys were conducted, with several individuals stating they used some form of basic antivirus software and believed this offered them complete protection against cyber criminals. The author suggests a need for the public to be more educated on the topic of Wi-Fi, making them aware of the risks to influence safer behaviours (Abdulkader, 2023). Whilst some strong points are made on the general thinking behind why users connect to public Wi-Fi networks, these are only lightly explored and reasons for these misconceptions are not investigated fully.

The continued risks of unsecured public Wi-Fi and why users keep using it: Evidence from Japan (Sombatruang et al., 2018)

These theories have been tested during practical experiments. During a study in Japan, researchers deployed a free Wi-Fi network at a number of locations and monitored the traffic over a 150-hour period. Using a range of networking tools and diagnostic equipment, they were able to view sensitive user data in real time. This included login credentials, email contents and other personal information. A number of individuals were also surveyed, and it was concluded that the average user is ignorant of the risks of using public Wi-Fi networks (Sombatruang et al., 2018). The paper is strong due to its evidence based approach, however there could be risk of ethical criticism due to lack of consent by the data collection method. Additionally, whilst

some behaviour traits and motivations will likely apply to users globally, the study itself only examines Japanese users so lacks breadth geographically.

A Nationwide Census on WiFi Security Threats: Prevalence, Riskiness, and the Economics (Gao, Yang, and Lee, 2021)

This subject matter has application worldwide, as shown by large international studies. One example leveraged a Wi-Fi network scanning app for Android across 14 million mobile devices, evaluating 19 million Wi-Fi access points for security. The study uncovered that 4% of access points showed signs of being compromised, which is notable due to prior smaller-scale studies estimating this closer to 1%. The report concluded that ad injection was the most common attack, usually due to HTTPS misconfiguration. Incentives for Wi-Fi network attackers were explored, uncovering an underground economy built around monetising malicious ad injection through compromised access points (Gao, Yang, and Lee, 2021). Whilst the report is the largest of its kind and covers the most countries, it is heavily skewed towards China (~99.5% of all APs analysed) and Asia (~99.8%). It's therefore not known how prevalent this would be in other parts of the world such as Western Europe, Africa or North America, although the USA only having 1.01% of compromised APs suggests this could be less prevalent.

Practicing Safe Public Wi-Fi: Assessing and Managing Data-Security Risks (McShane, Patel, and Smith, 2016)

With the risks of public Wi-Fi networks well evidenced, practical mitigation techniques that individuals can adopt have been investigated. Some include the use of VPNs to provide a secure tunnel for traffic. As a bare minimum, users should understand how to check if HTTPS is in use, either by actively looking whilst browsing or by using a modern web browser that blocks HTTP connections or visually warns the user when HTTPS is absent. Lastly, to combat account credential theft, users should make use of two-factor authentication wherever possible, ensuring intercepted passwords alone are insufficient to compromise an account (McShane, Patel, and Smith, 2016). The report makes recommendations achievable by the average user but places most responsibility on the individual, rather than encouraging ISPs or businesses operating public access points to mitigate risks themselves.

InSecurity in Wi-Fi Networks: A Systematic Review (Faíscas, 2022)

The most impact can be made by encouraging businesses to enhance the Wi-Fi networks they provide to the public. Instead of the user having to protect themselves when connecting to a coffee shop's Wi-Fi, how can the onus be placed on the coffee shop to more responsibly offer Wi-Fi to their customers. One way is to upgrade from WPA2 to WPA3, as although the latter is not faultless, it's a significant step in hardening the network. Some configuration options can help as well, including avoiding PSKs and instead implementing server-based authentication. The remaining recommendations are mainly geared towards protecting the business, for example segregating public traffic from staff traffic by using separate networks (Faíscas, 2022). The paper improves upon others by making a couple of suggestions that businesses can action to help protect their users, but is still mainly focused on securing the business itself, rather than directly protecting users. It makes only a brief mention of the challenges related to the WPA3 rollout such as hardware limitations and compatibility.

7 Research Methodology

7.1 Research Framework

The research framework used for this project was a narrative literature review, supported by thematic analysis of secondary research. This report did not involve any primary data collection. The project began with defining research questions around the problem. Once complete, a structured literature search was conducted. The collected literature was categorised by theme, in line with the thematic analysis. This framework was chosen for several reasons, partly due to time constraints limiting the feasibility of primary research. The chosen subject area is also well documented, having been widely studied for decades. A selective approach to literature ensured only high quality, reliable sources were used.

7.2 Data Collection and Analysis

This project primarily sourced literature from Google Scholar, with IEEE Xplore and ACM Digital Library used for validation where necessary. A variety of search terms were used to source relevant information, including: Public Wi-Fi security, WPA vulnerabilities, Public Wi-Fi user behaviour, and Wi-Fi security best practices. The target time frame was papers published within the last 10 years, to ensure an up-to-date understanding of the topic. That said, some papers were sourced outside this range to capture topics surrounding the protocol in earlier versions. Literature was selected with a preference for scientific papers and industry journals, and an attempt was made to capture a global scope for diversity. However, papers with real world experiments did result in bias towards Asia (primarily China and Japan). Once collected, the data was analysed as follows. The literature was categorised into four main themes: the evolution of Wi-Fi protocols, types of attacks, user behaviour and psychology, and attack mitigation techniques. Each paper had its main points summarised, then critiqued for possible limitations or gaps. When required, claims were cross-referenced between studies to ensure accuracy and reliability.

7.3 Social, Legal, and Ethical Issues

There are several issues surrounding this topic and the research process. The main social issue around public Wi-Fi security is lack of user awareness. This is a driving factor behind why individuals are most at risk. With one motivation for using public Wi-Fi being cost, there is a digital divide where some individuals must accept the risks due to limited alternatives. Additionally, the research process for this report resulted in some social bias by including more studies based in Asia, leaving other regions underrepresented. Legally, regulations like GDPR and the Data Protection Act have relevance to this topic. There is also debate concerning liability of Wi-Fi network owners if their users conduct illegal activities (Seymour, 2015). Lastly, it's important to note ethical concerns within this subject, such as determining whether the responsibility of safe browsing lies with the user or the network operator. During the research stage, several selected papers could be deemed ethically questionable due to capturing real-world Wi-Fi traffic, potentially without consent.

8 Findings and Future Directions

The major takeaway from the project is that, despite how the protocol has evolved over time in the face of constant threats, many attacks are still possible on public Wi-Fi networks. Even the latest version of the protocol, WPA3, has well-documented vulnerabilities. Barriers also

exist for the rollout of WPA3, with many networks using weaker versions of the protocol due to compatibility hurdles. Moreover, efforts are needed to educate the public on how they can adequately protect themselves. There is a disconnect between users having some perception of the risks but not altering their behaviour. The majority continue to connect to these networks without any protective measures in place, owing to convenience and cost factors. Another major finding from the literature review was that many applications still transmit unencrypted data that can be intercepted using basic tools like freely available packet sniffing software.

This research domain, in its current state, presents opportunities to advance understanding. Firstly, the subject of vulnerabilities is primarily covered from a theoretical standpoint, with limited coverage on real-world prevalence or rates of certain attacks. It is also difficult to quantify the impact of these attacks in measurable terms (e.g. quarterly value of monetary loss, yearly number of impacted individuals), as few papers have attempted to gather this data. Furthermore, improvements made to WPA3 are well covered, but there is less coverage on factors hindering more widespread adoption. Lastly, most threat mitigation techniques focus on what individuals can do, rather than exploring measures hotspot operators can implement to enhance security for all.

This project contributes to this domain by synthesising findings from two areas of public Wi-Fi: technological conditions and user psychology. Rather than focussing on one aspect in isolation, like enhancing encryption or increasing public awareness, this report takes a blended approach. Recognising that this is a multi-layered issue, recommendations are made at all levels, including advocating for policy changes, encouraging user behaviour change, and technical improvements.

There are recommendations for the future of this research area. Studies involving real-world experiments are only lightly covered, with significant gaps in experiments outside of Asia. Additionally, studies to determine prevalence of certain attacks would assist in prioritising areas like educational campaigns and countermeasure development.

9 Self-reflection

Prior to completing this project I had very little experience in the realm of computing research, so whilst there was a learning curve, I am pleased to now have the skills I do. Having the ability to take a subject, undertake a literature review, summarise findings and critically analyse for gaps is something I can now apply to similar projects in the future. This project also allowed me to hone my academic writing skills, including accurately citing sources and formally communicating technical subjects. It serves as a starting point for the route I am planning to take in computing, with a focus on networking and cybersecurity. I hope that completing a high-quality piece of research in this field will aid me in securing a corresponding graduate role, or even serve as a foundation for a path in research. My goal for the next 2 years is to continue immersing myself in this subject matter to strengthen my knowledge and pursue relevant industry certifications.

10 Conclusion

The primary objective of this project was to identify the risks associated with public Wi-Fi networks and how users could protect themselves. The research conducted spanned both technical specifications of protocols and related user behaviour. Despite many advancements, threats still exist today, and much of the responsibility remains with the user, as opposed to regulations that require hotspot operators to maintain secure networks. This study relied solely on secondary

research, but opportunities for expansion through first-hand data collection were identified, particularly to encompass the situation globally. Future efforts in this domain can therefore be summarised as follows:

- Increasing awareness amongst the public on the threats of public Wi-Fi
- Removing existing vulnerabilities in the latest version of the Wi-Fi protocol
- Improving compatibility of WPA3 to improve worldwide adoption
- Advocating for regulatory changes to oblige hotspot operators to maintain a minimum level of network security

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